

Effectiveness of Meta-Cognitive Strategy Training in Reducing English Language Anxiety

Hafiz Muhammad Nasarullah Mujahid

Higher Education Department, Punjab

mnm.pak@gmail.com

Muhammad Haroon Ahmad

School Education Department, Punjab

muhammadharoonahmad@gmail.com

Sarwat Rauf

PhD Scholar, Riphah International University, Faisalabad

Sarwatgujjar@hotmail.com

Nasir Ali

School Education Department, Punjab

nasiralidngra468@gmail.com

Sajida Nazir

School Education Department, Punjab

Sajidanazir61@gmail.com

Abstract

This research examines the effectiveness of metacognitive strategy training on English language anxiety among intermediate-level students of intermediate level in public sector colleges in Faisalabad, Punjab applying experimental research. Sixty-eight students of class 2nd year (session 2023-2024) were selected and assigned into an experimental and a control group at random. The experimental group underwent two months of metacognitive strategy training, whereas the control group was continued by normal teaching. For the measurement of English language anxiety in pre-training, post-training, and four-week follow-up, Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) was used. At the baseline, there were no significant differences between the groups, which proves the initial similarity. The paired sample t-test results indicated that there was a significant d in anxiety in the experimental group and no significant difference in the control group. ANCOVA findings also reported statistically significant and large effects in the experimental condition once the baselines have been controlled. The anxiety reduction was also observed in the follow-up, which proved the long-term impact of the intervention. The findings offer causal data on the effectiveness of training metacognitive strategies as an anxiety-sensitive and pedagogical intervention among intermediate-level EFL students.

Keywords: *meta-cognitive strategies, randomized controlled trial, English language anxiety*

1. Introduction

English language anxiety (ELA) is an affective construct that negatively influences the academic performance of English language learners, especially among the students of the public sector colleges in Pakistan (Ahmed et al. 2024; Bhatti et al., 2016). The existing studies on foreign language learning, English language anxiety is being presented as a dynamic emotional construct rather than a static characteristics of learner, which can be reduced through targeted pedagogical interventions (Abdullah et al., 2024). Modern intervention-based studies indicate that there is a strong association between anxiety reduction and the active involvement of students in a structured, thought-provoking and supportive learning environment (Wang, 2024).

The findings provided by Tabuchi et al. (2024) are significant in this regard, as they demonstrate that interventions tailored to individual needs can significantly decrease the level of language anxiety of language learners. Furthermore, this intervention also appears to have positive effects on the ability to speak, in low-skilled students, especially in a technology-mediated learning environment. The case study reveals that timely provision of corrective feedback, improved and safe opportunities for practice, and reduction in the severity of social threats serve as effective motivators to reduce anxiety. Although the study is limited in scope and specifically based on technology, it points to a fundamental pedagogical principle that is also applicable to metacognitive training, increasing the learner's awareness of the learning process and sense of control over their own performance can lead to a reduction in anxiety.

Similarly, the study by Bozorgian et al. (2024) demonstrates that metacognitive interventions through Dialogic Interaction (MIDI), effectively reduced the anxiety associated with listening in a foreign language as well as significantly improved the listening comprehension of EFL learners. The results from their combined research also indicate that reflective dialogue based on the use of strategies played an important role in normalizing cognitive difficulties, reducing fear of failure, and promoting emotional regulation and psychological improvement in learners. This study is important from the perspective of educational psychology, as it links anxiety reduction to metacognitive engagement and reflective processes, rather than just repetition or exposure to the teaching task, which explains the interrelationship of emotional and perceptual aspects of learning. The scope of scientific evidence and rigor of research is constantly expanding. The study by Muhammadpour et al. (2024) makes it clear that metacognitive intervention significantly increased not only listening skills but also metacognitive awareness levels in intermediate-level EFL students, and this effect was regardless of whether the students demonstrated high or low working memory capacity. It is particularly important from the point of view of educational psychology that clear and systematic metacognitive instruction effectively supported learners with limited cognitive ability, indicating that teaching interventions of this nature are capable of partially mitigating the impact of individual cognitive differences. Moreover, such instructions are also helpful in reducing the unnecessary cognitive load that increases anxiety. The results confirm the teaching value and cognitive comprehensibility of metacognitive strategy training at the inter level, especially in a setting whereby the learners are not psychologically and mentally prepared to meet the increasing language demands.

Hapsari (2020) confirmed that students who were given systematic and implicit training under metacognitive strategy instructional techniques performed significantly better in comprehension studies and reading autonomy than students who were taught under traditional teaching systems. It also reduces anxiety levels by increasing the perceptual control of the learners. In the same context, previous empirical studies also support these findings. For example, Taheri and Hedayat

Z (2018) showed that EFL students who attended a metacognitive strategy teaching program under the CALLA model performed significantly better than control groups in listening comprehension, as well as the benefits of stronger metacognitive awareness. This evidence confirms that metacognitive strategy instruction equally reinforces both the perceptual and emotional aspects of learning in accordance with the principles of educational psychology.

There is also a direct focus on the emotional aspect of strategic pedagogy. Marashi and Rahmati (2017) discovered that regular instruction of reading strategies effectively reduced pre-existing significant reading anxiety in EFL learners. The results suggest that strategic awareness can help reduce the emotional stress and negative emotions experienced in the process of learning. Although the quasi-empirical design of the study does not fully allow for conclusive findings of addiction, these results provide preliminary but empirically reliable evidence that the effects of tactical training are not limited to academic performance, but also have a direct impact on learners' anxiety.

The results of these interventions appear to be based on a strong theoretical and psychological basis. For example, a study by Kusiak (2001) shows that metacognitive strategy training leads to significant improvements in metacognitive knowledge, motivation, and comprehension in learners, and these effects are relatively more pronounced in low-skilled learners. From the perspective of educational psychology, it points out that metacognition teaching can be particularly effective during skill transition stages, as those stages are likely to show anxiety, self-doubt, and perceptual insecurity more acutely.

In a broader educational context, Ruiz de Zarobe and Smala (2020) characterize metacognitive awareness as a central connecting factor between learner self-regulated learning and instructional decision-making. This reflective process increases emotional involvement as well as results in metacognition as a fundamental and effective component of anxiety-sensitive pedagogy.

In addition, educational psychology points out that certain contextual and social factors such as the classroom environment and social interactions and also play an important role in the process of anxiety reduction, although these factors are distinct from strategy-based interventions. For example, Nagahashi (2007) demonstrated that cooperative learning-based teaching methods effectively reduce anxiety in the foreign language learning process by creating non-threatening and supportive learning situations. However, while such methods are effective pedagogically, their usefulness is usually limited to situations outside the classroom. Unless learners develop cognitive abilities of self-regulation and self-monitoring at an intrinsic level, interventions of this nature may fail to sustain the lasting effects of anxiety reduction.

These findings are theoretically supported by the conceptualization of foreign-language anxiety as a situational affective phenomenon. According to Horwitz, Horwitz and Cope (1986), language anxiety has cognitive, emotional and behavioral levels that disturb the performance and readiness to communicate. Future studies by MacIntyre and Gardner (1991) also revealed that anxiety also disrupts thought processes especially when one requires a long-term focused task. In this context, metacognitive strategies provide a direct and effective response to these psycho-cognitive disruptive factors, as the ability to manage cognitive load, monitor cognition, and control emotional responses enables learners to gain active control over various cognitive functions. (Sodhi, 2003).

The gaps are substantial despite the increasing evidence all over the world. A plethora of literature consists of case studies, quasi-experimental designs, or domain-specific interventions. (e.g. studies limited to listening or reading skills only). There are relatively few studies in educational psychology researches, that have used a Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) design, although this design is considered to be the most robust and effective for establishing the relationship between cause and effect (Shadish et al., 2002).

2. Rationale of the study

English language plays a significant role in academic advancement, admittance into tertiary education and socio-economic mobility in Pakistan. It has a status of compulsory subject and as a medium of instruction in post-secondary schooling. Regardless of its centrality, there is chronic underperformance at the intermediate level of English especially in the colleges of the public sector, and this is a significant issue in education as final results of Punjab Boards of Intermediate and Secondary Education (BISEs) confirms it. The Intermediate Part-I 2024 results show that there is a mild average success percentage of 52 (Lahore), 64.5 (Faisalabad), 51 (Sahiwal), and 51 (Gujranwala) that suggest that an average of 40-50 percent of pupils will fail at the Intermediate Part-I level every year (BISE Punjab, 2024). As much as these outcomes are the aggregate performance of subjects, English has always been one of the biggest failure subjects in intermediate examination.

Empirical literature review on the research on the public sector colleges in underdeveloped districts in Punjab has established several structural, pedagogic, and affective impediments to learning English language. According to Khan and Khan (2016), intermediate students in such districts as Mianwali and Bhakkar experience issues with the system, such as a lack of trained teachers, examination-oriented programs, low exposure to English and the absence of instructional materials, and a negative attitude of learners toward the language. These contextual limitations are further aggravated by the affective aspects, and in particular the anxiety in relation to English language (ELA) which has been revealed to considerably negatively affect the academic performance, attendance and the cognitive processing of the learners (Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope, 1986).

Moreover, the absence of empirical studies exploring metacognitive strategy training as a systematic and anxiety-reducing pedagogical intervention is conspicuous in the Pakistani educational context, specifically, the situation in the public sector intermediate colleges in Punjab and Faisalabad. This gap suggests that there is a necessity to have sound empirical studies, in accordance with the local educational and psychological realities, to develop evidence-based pedagogical approaches to help counter foreign language anxiety. In order to address these research gaps, the present study will be based on randomized controlled trial (RCT). To determine the causal relationship between metacognitive strategy training and English language anxiety in intermediate level students in Faisalabad, Punjab.

Furthermore, the study will also contribute to better understanding the process of anxiety-sensitive, strategic English language teaching in Pakistan's educational settings, resulting in relevant recommendations not only at the theoretical but also at the practical level. Thus, the research will make a significant contribution to elucidating the complex interactions of perceptual and emotional factors within the context of educational psychology, and introduce effective, evidence-based pedagogical strategies for educational policy makers, educators, and curriculum experts.

3. Null Hypotheses (H_0)

1. H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the baseline level of English language anxiety among students prior to the intervention.
2. H_{02} : There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of English language anxiety of students in the experimental group.
3. H_{03} : There is no significant difference in post-intervention English language anxiety levels between students in the experimental group and those in the control group.
4. H_{04} : Metacognitive strategy training does not have a significant causal effect on reducing English language anxiety among students

4. Research Design

To determine a causal relationship between metacognition strategy training and English language anxiety (ELA), the research study took a randomized controlled trial (RCT) design that is the standard of inferential causality in experimental research (Shadish et al., 2002). The RCT design provides strict manipulation of extraneous factors, the similarity of the study participants in the conditions, and an accurate characterization of the impacts of intervention. The pre-test posttest control group design was applied; the baseline levels were taken of ELA before the intervention and then after the intervention ELA levels were measured to quantify the changes that could be attributed to the training.

The design used in the study is a typical best practice in educational and psychological research on experimental studies, combining internal validity (randomization and controlled intervention) and ecological validity (by placing the research in real-life public-sector college classrooms).

4.1. Population and Sampling

This study population was 2nd year students (session 2023-2024) in public sector colleges in Faisalabad city, Punjab. It was due to the high rates of failure in English as reported by the Board of Intermediate and Secondary Education, Faisalabad (Faisalabad Board, 2024).

This research was consisted of two stages. The accessible population for this phase consisted of all enrolled students (N=6217) of these three colleges in Samundri city, whereas the data for need assessment was taken from 517 students who were available and consented to participate at the time of data collection. Stage (I) was carried out through a need analysis survey on 517 students from three public colleges, two boys and one girl, in Tehsil Samundri by using the Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS; Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope, 1986). The objective of this stage was to identify the students with high anxiety through

assessing the levels of English language among the students of three colleges. Results suggested that students from Government Graduate College (Boys) experienced higher level of anxiety in English language. On the basis of this analysis, GGC Boys college was selected purposively for experimentation. In Phase II, a sample of the students of the identified college was screened in order to reveal students with high levels of English language anxiety based on a pretested cutoff condition. Out of the eligible sample, 68 high-anxiety students were then identified and randomly split into an experimental group ($n = 34$) and a control group ($n = 34$), which is sufficient to consider moderate effects be identified in an experimental educational study (Cohen, 1992). Random assignment was used to establish the baseline equivalence, and reduce the selection bias.

4.1 Intervention

This experimental intervention involved a training program of metacognition strategy, which was specifically aimed at developing self-regulatory abilities of learners and minimizing the affective obstacles in the process of language acquisition. The theoretical basis of the intervention was Flavell metacognitive framework (1979) and Oxford language learning strategy taxonomy (1990).

4.5. Core components included

The eight-week intervention included two, 90 minutes planned instructions every week. Meanwhile, there was a control group that maintained their usual ways of instruction, hence isolating an effect of the new intervention type with confounding pedagogical factors. Experimental group was given instructional support according to present language learning objectives that would meet the SMART criteria. Methodological procedures through which systematic monitoring of comprehension, lexical acquisition and task execution were introduced. Appendage ranged activities were created that will allow learners to critically reflect on their repertoire of strategies, performance results and their affective responses.

Moreover, Situation-specific anxiety was alleviated by using cognitive-behavioral guided imagery, positive self-talk and rehearsal.

4.6. Procedure

In the first step, pre-test was completed by both experimental and control groups using Foreign Language Classroom Anxiety Scale (FLCAS) to establish baseline levels of English language anxiety and metacognitive strategy. After that, the participants were randomly assigned into the experimental or control group using a computer-generated sequence to ensure group equivalence. Experimental group was provided with structured metacognitive training and control group was provided with routine instruction. Four weeks after the intervention, a follow-up evaluation was performed on the strategies of metacognition as they were retained and the maintenance of the reduction of anxiety. immediately after the intervention of two months, the same instruments were used to measure change in anxiety levels and strategy application in both groups.

4.7. Data Analysis

Data analysis was done in SPSS version 28, and it was done under rigorous statistical procedures, suitable to experimental studies. In the first step, descriptive statistics and independent sample t-test were calculated to describe the characteristics and baselines of the groups. The paired-sample t-tests were used to compare changes in English language anxiety (ELA) pre-intervention and post-intervention within the experimental group. ANCOVA was used to compare the post-test anxiety scores of both experimental and control groups and controlling baseline differences. Cohen's d was computed the effect sizes in order to measure the magnitude of the intervention. Assumptions of normality, homogeneity and linearity were also tested before analysis to ascertain the validity of the statistical tests.

5 Results

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics for English Language Anxiety by Group and Measurement Occasion

Group	n	Pre-test M	Pre-test SD	Post-test M	Post-test SD	Follow-up M	Follow-up SD
Experimental	34	114.62	11.38	92.47	12.14	94.18	12.03
Control	34	113.91	10.97	111.26	11.45	110.84	11.62

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics of English Language Anxiety (ELA) in the pre-test, post-test, and follow-up phase of experimental and control group members. During the pre-test, both groups showed almost identical anxiety levels. The average score of the experimental group was (M = 114.62, SD = 11.38) and the average score of the control group was (M = 113.91, SD = 10.97). This initial similarity indicates that the random assignment of the groups was successful and that the initial factors of anxiety before the intervention were the same in both groups. After two months of metacognitive strategy training, the group receiving the experiment observed a significant decrease in ELA scores (M = 92.47, SD = 12.14), while the control group had only a slight decrease (M = 111.26, SD = 11.45), showing that the effects of metacognitive intervention are effective. Furthermore, during the four-week follow-up, the experimental group reported a low level of anxiety (M = 94.18, SD = 12.03), which was significantly lower than in the control group (M = 110.84, SD = 11.62).

5.2. Hypothesis Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the baseline level of English language anxiety among students prior to the intervention.

Table 2

Mean Comparison of Experimental and Control Groups on Baseline English Language Anxiety

Variables	Experimental Group		Control Group		t(66)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
English Language Anxiety	114.62	11.38	113.91	10.97	0.27	.79	0.07

Table 2 presents the results of the t-test, which was aimed at comparing the English Language Anxiety (ELA) scores during the pre-test among the experimental and control group members. In the pre-test phase, the average score of the experimental group was (M = 114.62, SD = 11.38) and the average score of the control group was (M = 113.91, SD = 10.97). The results showed that there was no statistically notable difference in baseline scores between the groups, $t(66) = 0.27$, $p = .79$, and the impact volume was very small, Cohen $d = 0.07$. These results confirm that the initial characteristics of the members of the two groups regarding English language anxiety were almost identical prior to the intervention. Thus, the expectation of a fundamental similarity of the groups turned out to be correct and provided a strong basis for further group comparison and evaluation of the effects of the intervention.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the pre-test and post-test mean scores of English language anxiety of students in the experimental group.

Table 3

Mean Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Scores on English Language Anxiety in the Experimental Group

Variable	Pre-test		Post-test		t(33)	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
English Language Anxiety	114.62	11.38	92.47	12.14	10.82	.00	1.86

$p < .001$.

Table 3 presents the results of paired t-test, which was aimed at examining the changes in English Language Anxiety (ELA) following metacognitive strategy training in experimental group. A significant difference was found between the average pre-test score (M = 114.62, SD = 11.38) and the average post-test score (M = 92.47, SD = 12.14). The decrease in anxiety was statistically

highly meaningful, $t(33) = 10.82$, $p < .001$, and the effect size was very large, Cohen's $d = 1.86$, indicating that metacognitive strategy training effectively and measurably reduced English language anxiety in the experimental group. These results clearly support that metacognitive strategy training acts as an effective intervention, which not only reduces the severity of anxiety.

Table 4

Mean Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Scores on English Language Anxiety in the Control Group

Variable	Pre-test		Post-test		$t(33)$	p	Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			
English Language Anxiety	113.91	10.97	111.26	11.45	1.21	.23	0.21

Table 4 presents the results of the paired-samples t-test for the control group, which was aimed at examining the changes in English Language Anxiety (ELA) during the intervention period. The results showed that the overall ELA score of the control group decreased slightly from pre-test ($M = 113.91$, $SD = 10.97$) to post-test ($M = 111.26$, $SD = 11.45$). However, this reduction was not statistically significant, $t(33) = 1.21$, $p = .23$. Furthermore, the effect size was also found to be low, as Cohen's $d = .21$ indicates that traditional teaching practices or the passage of time had a limited and non-significant effect on the reduction of English language anxiety. When these findings are compared with those of the experimental group (in Table 3), it becomes evident that significant reduce in anxiety cannot be explained due to time-based variables or conventional pedagogy. Instead, this decrease reflects the effects of more predictable metacognitive strategy training. Thus, these results support the unique and effective role of experiential intervention and confirm that metacognitive strategy training proved to be an effective and pedagogical-psychological intervention in reducing English language anxiety in intermediate-level students.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in post-intervention English language anxiety levels between students in the experimental group and those in the control group.

Table 5

Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) for Post-test English Language Anxiety Controlling for Pre-test Scores

Source	SS	df	MS	f	p	Partial η^2
--------	----	------	----	-----	-----	------------------

Pre-test						
Anxiety (Covariate)	2145.62	1	2145.62	28.91	< .001	.31
Group	3168.74	1	3168.74	42.67	< .001	.40
Error	4834.19	65	74.37			
Total		67				

Table 5 presents the results of the Analysis of Covariance, which was applied to compare post-test scores of English Language Anxiety (ELA) by controlling the baseline (pre-test) score as a covariate. The results showed that pre-test anxiety was significantly associated with post-test anxiety, $F(1,65) = 28.91, p < .001, \eta^2 = .31$, which indicates that the initial level of anxiety explained a large part of the variation observed in post-test anxiety. After controlling for pre-test scores, the effect of the group was also found to be statistically significant, $F(1,65) = 42.67, p < .001, \eta^2 = .50$. The results provide a significant statistical evidence of the causal effect of metacognitive strategy training on the reduction of English language anxiety in intermediate-level students. This intervention proved to be not only statistically meaningful but also of significant practical significance in the context of educational psychology, as it had positive and measurable effects on the cognitive and emotional aspects of learners.

Discussion and Conclusion

The results of the present research confirm that metacognitive strategy training is an effective intervention in reducing English language anxiety (ELA) in intermediate college students. Students who were taught goal-setting, self-monitoring, strategy assessment, and anxiety management techniques showed a significant reduction in anxiety compared to the control group who received standardized teaching. Moreover, the decreasing process continued during the follow-up phases, which revealed the long-term effects of the training. These results reflect that metacognitive strategies are also effective in improving cognitive performance. Before the intervention itself, the experimental and control groups did not show any notable differences in baseline ELA scores, indicating the internal validity of the study. This observation is in line with the results of previous studies, where the homogeneity of the groups at baseline ensures that the differences created after the intervention are not due to fundamental differences but to training (Shadish et al., 2002).

The experimental group's anxiety levels were significantly lower than those of the control group, whereas the control group's anxiety levels did not change. These findings are consistent with previous studies, which make it clear that metacognitive strategies, especially training based on goal setting, self-monitoring, and review of learned material, cause learners to increase confidence and decrease anxiety (Hapsari 2020). A comparison of the experimental and control group also showed that students who received structured metacognitive training had significantly lower ELA than students who received standardized instruction. Consequently, metacognitive strategy

training can serve as a practical, effective, and evidence-based intervention to reduce high levels of language anxiety in public sector intermediate colleges. This research not only adds to the theoretical knowledge of emotional regulation in the process of language learning, but also improves the emotional and academic performance of learners, providing concrete evidence for practical teaching strategies.

References

- Abdullah, M., Ashraf, M. N., Jabbar, A., Ahmad, M. S., & Mujahid, H. M. N. (2024). *The impact of English language anxiety on language learning motivation among madrassa students. Migration Letters*, 21(S13), 1332–1339. <https://migrationletters.com/index.php/ml/article/view/11706>
- Ahmed, S., Khan, D. S., Khan, D. W., & Asif, A. (2024). Exploring English language related anxiety in higher education context of Pakistan: Teachers' perspective. *Sindh Journal of Linguistics*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.58921/sjl.v3i1.49>
- Ali, S., Shakeel, S., & Shakir, F. (2021). Effects of anxiety in learning second language: A study on the public secondary school students. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 8(1), 1–15.
- Bhatti, N., Memon, S., & Pathan, H. (2016). Investigating the Perceptions of Pakistani English Language Learners on Language Learning Anxiety in EFL Classroom. *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, 7(5), 23–34. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1126872.pdf>
- BISE Punjab. (2024). *Intermediate Part-I annual examination results*. Boards of Intermediate and Secondary Education, Punjab.
- Bozorgian, H., Fallahpour, M. R., & Taghizade, M. (2024). Easing down foreign language listening anxiety: Metacognitive intervention and dialogic interaction. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijal.12586>
- Flavell, J. H. (1979). Metacognition and cognitive monitoring: A new area of cognitive–developmental inquiry. *American Psychologist*, 34(10), 906–911. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.34.10.906>
- Hapsari, A. D. (2020). Metacognitive strategy training in the teaching of reading comprehension: is it effective in efl classroom? *LangEdu Journal* 9(1). <https://jim.unisma.ac.id/index.php/LANG/article/viewFile/5091/pdf>
- Horwitz, E. K., Horwitz, M. B., & Cope, J. (1986). *Foreign language classroom anxiety*. The Modern Language Journal, 70(2), 125–132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1986.tb05256.x>

- Khan, T. J., & Khan, N. (2016). Obstacles in learning English as a second language among intermediate students of districts Mianwali and Bhakkar, Pakistan. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(2), 154–160. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jss.2016.42021>
- Kusiak, M. (2001). The effect of metacognitive strategy training on reading comprehension and metacognitive knowledge. *ELT Journal*, 55(2), 152–160. <https://doi.org/10.1075/eurosla.1.19kus>
- MacIntyre, P. D., & Gardner, R. C. (1991). Methods and results in the study of anxiety and language learning: A review of the literature. *Language Learning*, 41(1), 85–117. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-1770.1991.tb00677.x>
- Marashi, H., & Rahmati, P. (2017). The effect of teaching reading strategies on EFL learners' reading anxiety. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 8(4), 693–700. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.0804.08>
- Movahed, R. (2014). The effect of metacognitive strategy instruction on listening performance, metacognitive awareness, and listening anxiety of beginner EFL students. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 4(2), 88–99. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v4n2p88>
- Muhammadpour, M., Zafarghandi, A. M., & Tahriri, A. (2024). The effect of metacognitive intervention on the listening performance and metacognitive awareness of high- and low-working memory capacity EFL learners. *Journal of Psycholinguistic Research*, 53, Article 70. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10936-024-09917-6>
- Nagahashi, T. (2007). Techniques for reducing foreign language anxiety: Results of a successful intervention study. *Akita University Bulletin of Liberal Arts*, 62, 23–38. Retrieved from: <https://files01.core.ac.uk/download/pdf/144186582.pdf>
- Oxford, R. L. (1990). *Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know*. Heinle & Heinle.
- Ruiz de Zarobe, Y., & Smala, S. (2020). Metacognitive awareness in language learning strategies and strategy instruction in CLIL settings. *Journal for the Psychology of Language Learning*, 2(2), 20–35. <https://doi.org/10.52598/jpll/2/2/3>
- Shadish, W. R., Cook, T. D., & Campbell, D. T. (2002). *Experimental and quasi-experimental designs for generalized causal inference* (2nd ed.). Houghton Mifflin.
- Tabuchi, K., Kobayashi, S., Fukuda, S. T., & Nakagawa, Y. (2024). A case study on reducing language anxiety and enhancing speaking skills through online conversation lessons. *Technology in Language Teaching & Learning*, 6(3), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.29140/tltl.v6n3.1497>

- Taheri, P., & Hedayat Zade, M. (2018). The contribution of metacognitive strategies to EFL learners' listening comprehension task types. *Journal of Teaching English Language*, 12(2), 169–198. <https://doi.org/10.22132/tel.2018.82864>
- Wang, Y. (2024). An interactive online educational environment to reduce anxiety, improve emotional well-being, and critical thinking for college students. *Acta Psychologica*, 248, 104347. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104347>